

**STUDYING COOPERATIVE RELATIONSHIPS IN THE HUMANIZATION OF
RELATIONSHIPS IN THE TEACHER AND STUDENT SYSTEM**

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Abstract. *This article talks about cooperation in the education of the young generation, which is considered an important participant in the development of society, mainly in the humanization of relations in the teacher-student system.*

Keywords: *relations between teacher, student, teacher and student, humanization, pedagogical optimism, standing in the place of others.*

The current complex stage of the society's development, profound changes in the politics, economy, and social structure require a new approach to the education of the young generation and set new demands on them.

In the context of society recognizing the humanization of education as a priority task, there is a need to review its content, to focus on the comprehensive development of the individual, and to conduct multifaceted and large-scale research.

The priority task for the teacher is the relationship between the teacher and the student, and the implementation of this knowledge in the process of interaction with students in the classroom. Interaction addresses the following interrelated tasks:

- creating trusting relationships between teachers and students;
- organization of humanization trainings and provision of criteria for cooperation in decision-making among the participants;
- renewal of motivational resources of education;
- development of personal relationships of the teacher, the most adequate humanistic education;
- helping teachers and students in personal development.

In the formation of humanistic education, the personality plays an important role in teacher settings. In this regard, scientist K. Rogers distinguishes the following as the main ones:

- «openness» of the teacher for his thoughts, feelings, experiences, as well as the ability to openly express them in interpersonal communication with students;
- expressing the teacher's inner confidence in the abilities and talents of each student; In many ways, this setting corresponds to what is usually called "pedagogical optimism", "relying on the additional qualities of the student»;
- the teacher looks at the student's behavior, evaluates his reactions, actions, actions from the student's own point of view; This is the so-called "empathic understanding", which allows the teacher, in the words of the American scientist and teacher K.Rogers, to communicate with students, to everything around, including himself, children's It allows you to "stand in the place of others" by looking at yourself. Thus, in situations where the teacher understands and accepts the inner world of his students, behaves naturally, treats students with love according to

their inner experiences, he creates everything - the necessary conditions for humanistic communication.

The wealth of the pedagogical process is created by the deep knowledge of the teacher, the skill of organizing activities with the independent activity of students. And here is a single activity, united by its goals and motivation. And in this process, the teacher relies on the activity and independence of students, fully relies on their creative abilities, and predicts the results. Not only for students to read enthusiastically, to enter into relationships, to break standards, to include their own life experiences, but also to look for attractive perspectives in search of multiple solutions is considered a detriment to the teacher.

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